

A NEW ERA IN UZBEKISTAN SCULPTURE TRADITION AND MODERN SEARCHES

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the social, economic and cultural reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the formation and development of the art of sculpture and the activities of artists who contributed to the development of this art.

Keywords: work, portrait, artist, sculpture, tradition, genre, image, opportunity.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasidagi ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy va madaniyatga oid islohotlar, xaykaltaroshlik san'atining shakllanishi, rivojlanishi va ushbu san'atning rivojlanishiga hissa qo'shgan rassomlarning faoliyati haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: asar, portret, rassom, haykaltaroshlik, an'ana, janr, obraz, imkoniyat.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о социальных, экономических и культурных реформах в Республике Узбекистан, становлении и развитии искусства скульптуры и деятельности художников, внесших свой вклад в развитие этого искусства. Ключевые слова: произведение, портрет, художник, скульптура, традиция, жанр, образ, возможность.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts" Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 "Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts" dated April 21, 2020 No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time" 20th of 2021 Decree No. PD-6208 of April. It is

known that the 20th century was a period of sharp changes in the art of Uzbek music, “unconventional” compositional creativity and new forms of concerts appeared. In this regard, the concept of “variety” entered our circulation in musical culture.

The easel sculpture of Uzbekistan, which was formed within the framework of the art of multinational peoples until the 1990s of the 20th century, is currently developing under the influence of a purely local environment. This situation goes hand in hand with traditional and modern directions. The works of Azamat Khotamov, Anvar Rakhmatullaev, Leonid Ryabtsev, Marina Borodina, Mukhtar Musaboev, Damir Roziboev, Ulug'bek Mardiev, Roberd Avakyan, Jalaliddin Mirtojiev, Akhmad Shaymurodov, Tolagan Yorkulov, Ulash Urokov, Tolagan Tozhikhojayev in portrait, historical and thematic genres of the traditional direction deserve attention. For example, “Al-Khorazmi” by A. Rakhmatullaev (plaster, 2004), “Ibn Sino” (plaster, 2004), “Kim pen hwa” (plaster, 2006), “Self-Portrait” by L. Ryabtsev (plaster, 1996 y), M. Aliev’s “Portrait of a Man” (plaster, 2006), M. Borodina’s “Vosit Vokhidov” (bronze), “Alisher Navoi” (plaster) U. Mardiev’s “Tilab Makhmudov” (bronze, 2002) and portraits of contemporaries made a worthy contribution to the development of the genre. In the thematic genre, which has many possibilities in terms of visual expression, the manifestation of new research can be observed in the work of Azamat Khotamov. In particular, being free from elementalization of the image and showing strong emotional images on the basis of a holistic form became a characteristic characteristic of his work. The composition can be found in music, theatre, photography, literature, and all kinds of fine arts. [4]

In the framework of this trend, the poetic method approach has become somewhat active in the work of some sculptors. Forms showing elegant plastic movement were created and spiritual moments that reached a certain state were glorified. For example, T. Tozhikho'jaev's “Moving along the wave” (bronze, 2002), “Donishmand” (Shamot, 2003), “Kurash” (1998, bronze, granite), “Girl carrying a jug” (2000, gypsum), “Motherhood” (1991, stone, onyx), J. Mirtojiev “Babur-Vatan soginchi” (1996, bronze), “Sayar Babur” (2000, bronze), Ulash Urokov's “Dream” (1992), “Poet” (1993), “Woman in National Dress” (1994), “Lovers” (1996), “Waiting” (1997) can be an example of this.

The traditional-creative principle of the new era was not limited to this, serious results were also achieved in the thematic genre. In particular, in this genre, the ways of interpretation with a plastic incremental level (that is, exaggerating the idea in form) and a compositional approach were formed and rose to a leading

position in the work of some sculptors. The main criteria for development are the figurines of the second type of local sculptors, decorative ornaments and garden sculptures [5]. In particular, K. Norkhorozov's "Dedication to the disabled: a cry" (1990), "Heart cry" (2001), "Heart sound" (1994), A. Khotamov's "Surkhondarya gozali" (2003), M. Borodina's "Female Design" (1997), "Mannequin Statue" (1998), "Mazkharabozchilar" (1999), T.Yorkulov's "Self Portrait" (1996), A.Abraev's "Capricorn" (2000), A.Aliev's Among them are sculptures called "Grandmother" (2006).

Also, the abstract compositional approach observed in this genre is also sharply different from the traditions of the previous stage with its pictorial characteristics. Although the rapid development in this genre is not high, the aspects related to the new artistic process are significant. Already, before 1990, sculptors expressed human body movements and its features as the main object, now they depict composite generalized images ("World of Art", Azamat Khotamov, 2004), "Symbolic Birds" (T. Tojiho'jaev, 2000), "Ratkha-Krishna", U. Mardiev, 2003) also drew attention. This is achieved through the mental and spiritual development of the students.[6]

From the end of the 20th century, new opportunities for the development of the modern direction appeared in easel sculpture. In particular, with the establishment of the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan in 1997, the regular holding of national and international exhibitions accelerated the process of implementing modern directions. Also, from the late 1990s, he activated postmodernist thinking and creative practice. From this time, it became apparent that among the sculptors, they paid more attention to modernity than to traditional approaches. Finally, as a result of the promotion of initiative approaches by some leading sculptors, new creative approaches began to develop. In this regard, the works of Bayot Mukhtorov and his students Risdovlat Abdullaev, Zinnur Gayfullin, Akrom Toraev, Aleksey Toroppov, and Aleksey Protopopov became significant. With their new creative views, they made a worthy contribution to the development of easel sculpture, as well as introduced the technique of working with new materials in exhibition sculpture, raising the overall development status. B. Mukhtorov's works such as Guardian of the Bells (enamel, metal, stained glass), "Story about Saihun" (enamel, metal, stained glass) and "Journey to Sijjak" (enamel, metal, wood, leather) have these features.

From the 2000s, the plastic composite devices of the installation flow, which were presented at the International Biennale exhibitions, did not escape the

artistic thinking of sculptors. On the contrary, it had a significant impact on the work of some artists and provided an appeal to modern principles. For example, in 2007, at the exhibition “Constallation” held at the “Uzbekistan Fine Art Gallery”, it was felt that the advanced principles developing in the modern process were mastered by young artists such as Farrukh Akhmadaliev, Fanis Akhmedzyanov, Vladimir Elizarov, Oktam Saidov. Directing the activities of young sculptors entering the creative process to increasing the weight of national approaches in the development of the field can be included as future tasks.

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